

Complexes of Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) with Biacetyldihydrazone

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A number of biacetyldihydrazone metal complexes of the type, $M(\text{BDH})_2\text{X}_2$ (where $M = \text{Ni(II)}$, Co(II) ; $\text{X} = \text{Br}^-$, I^- , SCN^- , NO_3^- , BF_4^- and $\text{BDH} = \text{biacetyldihydrazone}$) have been isolated by metal ion catalysed template syntheses. The complexes possess characteristic colours and are non-hygroscopic, sparingly soluble in water and can be stored for a long period without decomposition. The infrared spectra show considerable metal to ligand π electron interactions which are manifested by the shift of the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ bond stretching vibrations to a higher frequency region. The complexes are found to be spin free paramagnetic with nearly octahedral arrangement of the ligand atoms about the metal ions.

BIS and tris complexes of biacetyldihydrazone with iron(II) chloride and iodide and bis complexes with cobalt(II) and nickel(II) chlorides have been reported by Busch and Stoufer^{1,2}. Biacetyldihydrazone possesses structure analogous to dimethylglyoxime and forms five membered chelate rings with the above mentioned metal ions. In a recent study from our laboratory, it has been shown that DMG metal complexes employ N-O groups in bonding³. Because of the similarity in structure of biacetyldihydrazone with dimethylglyoxime, there exists the possibility to prepare metal cluster complexes employing biacetyldihydrazone metal complexes as ligands. With this objective, a programme of work is being currently undertaken and in the present communication, we describe a series of bis biacetyldihydrazone metal complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) with Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , SCN^- and BF_4^- as anions along with earlier reported chloro complexes.

Experimental

Biacetyl was of E. Merck quality. Hydrazine hydrate was of BDH make. All the compounds have been prepared under similar experimental conditions. A typical preparation is described here.

Bis(biacetyldihydrazone) nickel(II) nitrate :

Biacetyl (1.7 g, 0.02 mole) in alcohol was treated dropwise with an alcoholic solution of nickel nitrate hexahydrate (2.9 g, 0.01 mole). The resulting mixture was warmed to boiling and hydrazine hydrate (2.0 g, 0.04 mole) was added dropwise with constant stirring when a blue precipitate was readily formed. It was refluxed over a hot water bath for about two hours. The compound was cooled, filtered, washed successively with alcohol and ether and dried at room temperature. Yield was almost quantitative in each case.

The compounds were analysed for different constituents by standard procedures⁴. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility was measured using a Guoy balance. The analytical data, colour and magnetic moment of each compound are recorded in Table 1. The infrared absorption bands of the compounds have been taken using Perkin Elmer 221 and 225 infrared spectrophotometers and important i. r. data are recorded in Table 2. The electronic spectra in visible range were taken using Beckmann spectrophotometer; the spectral bands are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA, COLOURS AND MAGNETIC MOMENTS OF THE COMPLEXES OF NICKEL(II) AND COBALT(II) WITH BIACETYLDIHYDRAZONE

Sl. No.	Formula of the complexes	Colours	Metal %		$\text{N}_2\text{H}_4\%$		$\text{X}^- \%$		Magnetic moments μ_{eff} in B. M.
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
1.	NiL_2Cl_2	Blue	16.3	16.5	34.2	35.8	20.0	19.8	3.16
2.	NiL_2Br_2	Bluish violet	13.6	13.2			35.5	35.8	3.18
3.	NiL_2I_2	Violet	11.1	10.9			47.0	46.9	3.22
4.	$\text{NiL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	Pink	15.0	14.8	31.8	31.4			3.30
5.	$\text{NiL}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Pink	15.0	15.0	31.2	31.5	15.3	15.5*	3.20
6.	$\text{NiL}_2(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Violet	11.1	11.9	26.8	28.0			3.14
7.	CoL_2Cl_2	Light violet	16.2	16.5	34.9	35.8	20.0	19.8	5.10
8.	CoL_2Br_2	Pink	14.0	13.2			35.4	35.8	5.14
9.	CoL_2I_2	Pink	10.3	10.9	22.2	23.6	46.8	46.9	5.20
10.	$\text{CoL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	Brick red	15.0	14.8	30.9	31.4			5.18
11.	$\text{CoL}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	Reddish Pink	14.8	15.0	30.5	31.5	14.8	15.5*	5.16
12.	$\text{CoL}_2(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Pink	12.6	11.9	27.0	28.0			5.20

* % of Sulphur

TABLE 2—PRINCIPAL i. r. ABSORPTION BANDS FOR NICKEL(II) AND COBALT(II) COMPLEXES WITH BIACETYLDIHYDRAZONE (FREQUENCIES IN cm^{-1})^a

NiL_2Br_2	NiL_2I_2	$\text{NiL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$\text{NiL}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	$\text{NiL}_2(\text{BF}_4)_2$	CoL_2Br_2	CoL_2I_2	$\text{CoL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$\text{CoL}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	$\text{CoL}_2(\text{BF}_4)_2$	Tentative band assignments
3315 s	3325 s	3320 s	3340 s	3330 s	3305 s	3300 s	3315 s	3312 s	3330 s	ν as NH_2
3240 m	3250 m	3270 m	3260 m	3260 m	3270 m	3235 m	3245 m	3250 m	3230 m	ν s NH_2
2940 w	2940 w	2940 w	2945 w	2920 sh	2910 w	2900 sh	2900 w	2900 w	2910 w	ν C—H
—	—	—	2100 s	—	—	—	—	2110 s	—	ν C \equiv N
1630 m	1625 sh	1632 m	1620 m	1630 m	1635 m	1615 sh	1640 m	1635 m	1630 m	δ NH_2
1615 s	1600 m	1612 m	1605 s	1610 s	1605 s	1595 m	1620 s	1600 s	1610 s	ν C=N
1410 s	1420 m	1400 m	1430 s	1440 s	1405 s	1400 m	1415 m	1440 s	1435 s	δ as C—CH ₃
1370 m	1375 m	1365 m	1380 s	1375 m	1375 m	1380 m	1365 m	1380 m	1370 m	δ s C—CH ₃
—	—	1030 s	—	—	—	—	1035 s	—	—	} ν N—O
—	—	1240 s	—	—	—	—	1245 s	—	—	
720 w	700 m	730 m	760 m	760 w	700 m	730 m	710 m	772 m	740 m	ν B—F
—	—	—	—	995 s	—	—	—	—	1000 s	δ r NH_2

^a s = strong, m = medium, sh = shoulder, w = weak, L = biacetyldihydrazone.

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF NICKEL(II) AND COBALT(II) COMPLEXES WITH BIACETYLDIHYDRAZONE (cm^{-1})^a

Formula of the complexes	${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$	${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}$	Formula of the complexes	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$
NiL_2Cl_2	16,000	19,000	CoL_2Cl_2	16,000
NiL_2Br_2	15,100	18,200	CoL_2Br_2	16,100
NiL_2I_2	14,700	18,900	CoL_2I_2	15,200
$\text{NiL}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	16,100	18,500	$\text{CoL}_2(\text{SCN})_2$	15,700
$\text{NiL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	15,700	18,000	$\text{CoL}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$	16,100
$\text{NiL}_2(\text{BF}_4)_2$	14,800	18,700	$\text{CoL}_2(\text{BF}_4)_2$	15,800

^a L = Bi. cetyldihydrazone spectra were taken using nujol mull and aqueous solutions

Results and Discussion

Infrared spectra :

Infrared spectra of the complexes show similar features indicating that all the complexes are isostructural. The spectra of the chloro complexes of nickel(II) and cobalt(II) agree well with the spectra reported by Busch and Stoufer² except a few additional bands observed for their compounds, which obviously arise due to stretching and deformation vibrations of water molecules associated with the compounds reported by them.

A number of regular changes are apparent upon comparing the spectrum of biacetyldihydrazone with the spectra of the complexes with cobalt(II) and nickel(II) salts. The most important characteristic feature of the spectra in the region 3400-3200 cm^{-1} is the appearance of two strong bands which may be assigned to asymmetric and symmetric stretching modes of vibration of uncoordinated NH_2 group of the hydrazone. The position of these bands in the complexes as compared to that in the free ligand is slightly shifted towards lower frequency region with reduced intensity. A similar trend is reported by Busch and Stoufer² for the complexes of biacetyldihydrazone with nickel(II) and cobalt(II) chlorides. This change in position and intensity may be accorded to the change in the extent of interaction of nitrogen atom of the uncoordinated NH_2 group with the imine nitrogen on coordination with the metal ions.

The next pair of bands of structural significance appears in the region 1650-1580 cm^{-1} . Considering the intensity, sharpness and position, the more intense and sharp band at lower frequency is assigned to C—N stretching vibration. The ν C—N band for the free ligand is observed at \sim 1580 cm^{-1} which shifts to a higher frequency region in the metal complexes and appears at \sim 1615 cm^{-1} . The shifting of this band to higher frequency region clearly indicates the increase in the bond order of the C—N bond which may arise due to increase in conjugation of the π electron system⁵. The d-electrons of the central metal ions seem to have transferred to the orbitals of the ligand participating in conjugation. This metal to ligand π electron interaction is exhibited by the shift of the ν C—N band to higher frequency region. The other relatively less sharp band appearing \sim 1635 cm^{-1} is attributed to the $-\text{NH}_2$ deformation vibration. In complexes with some of the anions, for example I^- , it appears in the form of a shoulder.

Next, a group of two bands appear in the region 1470-1370 cm^{-1} . The relatively stronger band in the region 1460-1440 cm^{-1} may be attributed to asymmetric C—CH₃ deformation vibration whereas the weaker band in the vicinity of 1370 cm^{-1} can be assigned to symmetric C—CH₃ deformation vibration. As compared to the spectrum of the free ligand, the intensity of the band due to symmetric C—CH₃ deformation vibration is decreased whereas the intensity of the band due to asymmetric C—CH₃ deformation vibration remains almost unaffected. As regards the position of these

bands, they suffer slight shift, the mode of shift being somewhat irregular.

The bands due to $-\text{NH}_2$ rocking vibration appear in the region $740\text{--}660\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The first band which appears at $\sim 740\text{ cm}^{-1}$ experiences an irregular shift among the spectra of the complexes whereas the second absorption band $\sim 665\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is shifted to slightly higher frequency region.

In addition to these vibrational bands, a few additional bands have been observed in the spectra of complexes with nitrate, thiocyanate and fluoroborate salts which can be attributed to the $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ of the nitrate group, $\nu_{\text{C}\equiv\text{N}}$ of the thiocyanate group and $\nu_{\text{B-F}}$ of the fluoroborate group respectively. Some of the bands due to these groups which are not observed as additional bands might have overlapped with the bands of biacetyl-dihydrazone.

In the i. r. spectra of nitrate complexes two additional bands have been observed, one in the region $1035\text{--}970\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and other in the region $1290\text{--}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which can be attributed to the $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ of the NO_3^- group. The third band which is expected to appear for the $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ in the region $1530\text{--}1480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ appears to have been overlapped with the deformation vibration of C-CH_3 group. By comparing the spectra with known unidentate and bidentate nitrate complexes⁶, it is concluded that the nitrate group is coordinated in an unidentate manner in the nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes.

Thiocyanato complexes show a very weak band in the region $870\text{--}850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ vibration. Because of its low intensity and the appearance of other skeletal vibrations of the ligand groups, it is not possible to make an unambiguous diagnosis and their usefulness for structural analyses. However, a strong band at $\sim 2100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ originating due to $\nu_{\text{C}\equiv\text{N}}$ stretching vibration of the SCN group, provides self consistent information concerning the coordination of the thiocyanate group with the central metal ion. The appearance of this band at $\sim 2100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggests SCN group to be coordinated as a terminal group and not as a bridging group since $\nu_{\text{C}\equiv\text{N}}$ frequency of a bridging thiocyanate group appears at 2200 cm^{-1} ^{7,8}. It has also been found that $\nu_{\text{C}\equiv\text{N}}$ appears at a lower frequency ($\sim 2100\text{ cm}^{-1}$) when the SCN group coordinates through nitrogen atom as compared to coordination involving sulphur atom ($\sim 2200\text{ cm}^{-1}$). Therefore, it is logical to conclude that the bonding of the SCN group has taken place through nitrogen atom in the present group of complexes.

Several workers have studied the spectra of fluoroborate salts and have observed an intense band in the region $990\text{--}1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (assigned to ν_3) and a series of very weak bands at $\sim 353, 525$ and 770 cm^{-1} ¹⁰. In the present case, an intense band is observed at 990 cm^{-1} which can be attributed to the ν_3 vibration of the BF_4^- group. Other bands are rather weak and have been located with a slight shift of their positions as compared to the spectra of BF_4^- ionic salt and indicate that the fluoroborate group is coordinated to the central

metal ion through one of the fluorine atoms of the BF_4^- group.

These results clearly manifest the mode of bonding of biacetyl-dihydrazone and the complexes are believed to possess the structure as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1.

X = Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , O atom of NO_3^- , N atom of SCN^- and F atom of BF_4^- ; M = Co(II), Ni(II).

Magnetic susceptibility: The nickel(II) complexes are of spin free type having magnetic moments 3.2 B.M. The data manifests nearly octahedral coordination of ligand atoms about nickel(II) ion. The cobalt(II) complexes possess magnetic moments 5.2 B.M, which corresponds to octahedral stereochemistry about the metal ion.

Electronic spectra: Electronic spectra of the complexes have been studied in the visible region using nujol mull and aqueous solutions. The data are recorded in Table-3. The visible absorption spectra of nickel(II) complexes with biacetyl-dihydrazone show the characteristic features of a complex with octahedral symmetry with certain amount of tetragonal distortion. Two bands have been observed in the region $14000\text{--}19000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The lower frequency band can be assigned to ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \leftarrow {}^3\text{B}_{1g}$ and the higher one to ${}^3\text{E}_g \leftarrow {}^3\text{B}_{1g}$ transitions where ${}^3\text{A}_{2g}$ and ${}^3\text{E}_g$ are the two split components of ${}^3\text{T}_{1g}$ state in octahedral field upon tetragonal distortion.

The ground term for Co(II) ion is ${}^4\text{F}$ and next higher quartet level ${}^4\text{P}$ lies nearly 15000 cm^{-1} above it¹¹. In an octahedral field, ${}^4\text{F}$ level splits into ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}$, ${}^4\text{T}_{2g}$ and ${}^4\text{A}_{2g}$ whose energy levels increase successively and ${}^4\text{P}$ term transforms as ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}$. Though electronic spectra of several Co(II) complexes have been reported¹², their assignments have not been always unambiguous. The ligand field transitions ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}$ (F) and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}$ (P) \leftarrow ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}$ (F) appear in the visible region of spectra, the former being always weak is scarcely observed. On the other hand, the latter appears as relatively intense band with some amount of structure. The present series of compounds exhibit a multiplet band structure in the region $16000\text{--}19000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the band width spreading over ca. 3000 cm^{-1} . The band can be assigned to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}$ (P) \leftarrow ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}$ (F) transition and the structure manifests tetragonal distortion of the complexes.

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